

Qualitative Study on Integration of Exercise Therapy and Information and Communication Technology (ICT) Devices for Healthy Workforce in Nigeria

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Abstract

Participation in regular physical activity has been demonstrated to reduce all-cause mortality, prevent cardiovascular disease, regulate blood pressure, and weight control among others. In today's society, individuals can easily fall into the trap of developing a sedentary lifestyle as a result of choosing the easy way out in one's daily activities coupled with the hectic lifestyle which prevents one from engaging in regular physical activity. Due to the high prevalence of physical inactivity, increased levels of physical activity are a global public health priority. This paper presents a qualitative study into the varying functions and roles played by exercise therapy and information and communication devices in advancing healthy workforce. The advent of technology-based innovations has further brought about various ways of staying physically active regardless of constraints that might be encountered during the course of one's daily activities, with the presence of tracking devices for physical activity levels and other tools, acting as testaments to this. It is thus, recommended that individuals be informed and made aware of the need for active participation in physical activities for optimum health. Also, development of fitness centres should be encouraged to bring about mass involvement in physical activity irrespective of age groups. A healthy nation is a wealthy nation and as such, the need for a proactive approach towards health is required, as it has a backdrop effect on the sustainability of the nation's economy.

Keywords: Physical activity, Fitness, Health, Mortality, Technology, Economy, Nation

Introduction

Over the past years, there has been a huge shift from a lifestyle that was, by definition, physically active to one that is predominantly sedentary. It is well acknowledged that, engaging in physical activity is a crucial means of improving the physical and mental health of individuals. According to Riseth and Colleagues (2019), the effects of physical activity to improve or maintain good health are well documented. Despite public health recommendations and encouraging advice to stay physically active, approximately 30% of adults worldwide are physically inactive (Riseth, Torunn, Tom & Aslak, 2019). Exercise therapy is the practice of using physical activities to enhance physical function and health status (or reduce or prevent disability) in order to help patients or clients reach better levels of functionality at home, school, workplace, or community. It also includes activities that allow healthy clients to improve or maintain their health or performance status (for work, recreational, or sports purposes) and prevent or minimize future potential health problems (Bandy & Sanders, 2001). In recent times, technology-based innovations have advanced participation in physical activity through the use of tracking devices for physical activity enhancement, statistical tools for evaluation and feedback, and visual interactive demonstrations for analyzing playbacks. Tracking devices can aid athletic performance by utilizing sensors and chips that aid in evaluating skill and movement through Computer Aided Designs (CAD) which gives room for virtual design and testing techniques to be effected on all aspects of physical activity, sport and equipment research and development (Buchheit, Allen, Modonutti, Gregson, & Di Salvo, 2014). Hence, there is the need to widely emphasize on the varying potentials and benefits accruable from active participation in exercise and the role of ICT devices in further enhancing fitness.

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Exercise Therapy and Health Promotion

World Health Organization [WHO] (1948), defined health as a complete state of physical, mental and social well-being and not merely the absence of sickness or disability. Physical activity can promote health and prevent the onset of disease including cardiovascular disease, type 2 diabetes and osteoporosis, forms of cancer, obesity and injury. Participation in physical activity is also known to improve mood, reduce stress and anxiety while also improving self-confidence, self-esteem, energy levels, sleep quality and the ability to concentrate (Mallikarjun & Vijaykumar, 2017). In a similar fashion as stated by Bandy & Sanders (2001), exercise therapy seeks to achieve the following goals; 1) Increase the normal range of motion 2) Improve and strengthen weak muscles 3) Improve the performance in daily activities 4) Release contracted muscles, tendons, and fascia 5) Mobilize joints 6) Improve circulation 7) Improve respiratory capacity 8) Improve coordination 9) Improve balance 10) Increased motor or sensory function 11) Reduction of medication, reduction of hospital visits, and increased overall health and 12) Improve exercise performance and functional capacity (endurance). All these goals are achieved through the participation in exercises targeting one's range of motion (passive, active and assisted active), flexibility, strength, aerobic and proprioceptive or neuromuscular improvement (Nagavani, 2013). Any exercise that tackles a restriction in natural motion at a joint or tissue interface can increase range of motion. Exercises can be done through the application of passive, active assisted, or active range of motion utilized to provide controlled stress to a joint and can be modulated by a number of factors including injury to muscle, tendon, ligament, joint capsule, and soft tissue structures. When connective tissues are not stretched, the soft tissues gradually shorten, which impairs range of motion and causes disuse-related impairments. Therefore, gentle A/AA/P range of motion should be initiated to avoid the vicious cycle of pain, immobility, contracture, and overall impaired function (Nagavani, 2013). Stretching is generally incorporated during range of motion exercises in order to facilitate improvements in mobility, with McKenzie and May (2003), stating the existence of three common types of stretching; static, passive and dynamic. Many different strengthening modalities exist and may include elastic or resistance bands, body weight and/or gravity-based resistance, manual resistance, and weights in the form of dumbbells, bars, or machines to name a few. The American College of Sports Medicine (ACSM, 2015) formulated minimal requirements to evaluate the quality of training programs for effective muscle strength training in healthy adults. The ACSM recommends a progressive individualized program, for all major muscle groups with at least 1 set of 8 to 12 repetitions and a frequency of 2 to 3 days a week.

Aerobic exercise, also known as endurance training, is defined as any exercise designed to increase cardiovascular fitness, often described as an increase in the maximal uptake of oxygen (Madden, 2013). This entails rhythmic, repeated, and continuous movements of the same large muscle groups for at least 10 minutes at a time. Aerobic exercise stimulates the heart rate and breathing rate to increase in a way that can be sustained throughout the exercise session. Examples of aerobic exercises include cardio machines, spinning, running, swimming, walking, hiking, aerobics classes, dancing, cross country skiing, cycling and many others. Aerobic exercise has long been noted as a key tool in the prevention and treatment of many of the chronic diseases typically associated with old age. These include impaired glucose tolerance, hypertension, heart disease and osteoporosis. Regular and moderate aerobic exercise increases certain antibodies in the blood called immunoglobulins which ultimately strengthens the immune system. Aerobic exercise may slow the loss of brain tissue and improve cognitive performance. (Ashley, 2020).

Proprioceptive exercise training, sometimes called functional fitness training, incorporates motor skills such as balance, coordination, gait and agility training. In the elderly, Tai chi has been shown to improve balance and reduce the risk of falls. In female athletes, there are anterior cruciate ligament injury prevention programs that focus on functional strength, balance, and neuromuscular control. The use of BOSU balls, foam pads, and unstable surfaces can be used to progressively challenge balance while performing functional activities to train the integrated balance system, therefore potentially reducing the risk of lower limb injury (Jurkiewicz, Marzolini, & Oh, 2011). Aquatic exercise, Pilates, Tai-Chi and even Yoga may be considered as functional activities to complement the therapeutic exercise.

ICT-Based Approach to Physical Activity and Fitness Testing

Anmol (2014), described information and communication technologies (ICT) as forms of technologies that are used to create, store, share or transmit, exchange information which spans across technologies such as: radio, television, video, telephone, satellite systems, computer and network hardware and software; as well as the equipment and services related with these technologies. Information and communications technology (ICT) in the field of exercise and sport science makes use of various technological tools and resources to produce, distribute, store and manage information and knowledge (Majoka, Fazal, & Khan, 2013). Sport & exercise science focuses on comprehending and interpreting individual responses and adaptations to muscular activity, with the goal of enhancing sports performance, reducing the risk of injury and enhancing the health and

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wellbeing of individuals. It involves the study of biomechanics, nutrition, exercise and assessment of health and exercise. With physical inactivity being the fourth highest leading risk-cause of mortality on a global level while also increasing the risk of many chronic diseases and conditions (WHO, 2009). The advent of innovation like ICT gadgets and services (pedometers, accelerometers, mobile in-built accelerometers, heart rate monitors, body-fat monitors, social networking, sport gaming and computer-based counseling systems, global positioning technologies, and mobile entertainment electronics) have greatly improved people's access to information about their body and state of health (Koskivaara, Laukkanen & Heinonen, 2011).

Technology is now being used to increase the number of people involved in physical activity and sport, as well as to enhance the performance of those people. With the production of new equipment, resources, and tools; sport participation and performance have become significantly improved. The combination of information technology in mass sports has experienced a substantial development, with the application of virtual reality technology to create virtual reality information in fitness equipment; such as network virtual reality treadmill, digital tennis, boxing. Through the guidance of fitness experts, internet users can also sum up a set of effective fitness methods for themselves with experts suggesting that internet-based physical activity interventions should be used by clinicians to promote and change exercise behavior (Marcus, Ciccolo & Sciamanna 2009). This kind of economical and efficient fitness demand brought by information technology makes the sport/fitness world experience fast rising growth.

Fitness trainers are expected to understand how computers and other technological devices can contribute to data collection for the analysis of movement patterns, sport skills, evaluation of student learning, and assessment of health-related physical fitness. This includes using exercise equipment to evaluate physical activity (e.g., accelerometers, heart rate monitors, pedometers, interactive dance machines), body composition (e.g., bioelectrical impedance devices, electronic skin-fold calipers) (Woods, Karp, Miao, & Perlman, 2008). A fitness test is any method of gathering information about the health and physical capability of an individual, with the measurement and evaluation of the different components of fitness allowing for the planning of effective training sessions and programmes for individual performers or individuals within groups, squads and teams.

Reasons for Fitness Testing

Some of the reasons for fitness testing include but not limited to: 1) as a measure of general health 2) to set realistic training goals and provide feedback on the effectiveness of a training programme 3) provides a means of talent identification, comparison of performance / performers and preparation for competition and 4) To motivate the athlete / performer (Woods et al., 2008).

ICT Tools/Devices and their Roles in Fitness Testing

The most common technology devices used in day-to-day fitness testing today are pedometers and heart rate monitors. With the increase in obesity levels, technologies for measuring activity levels have become prominent. Pedometers, accelerometers, and heart rate monitors can be used to track physical activity levels and collect useful information concerning exercise intensity and/or duration (Mears, 2010).

Pedometers are sensor-based devices which counts and monitors the number of steps taken throughout the day. Most pedometers provide a fairly accurate count of steps taken during ambulatory activities such as walking, jogging, and running. To provide accurate step counts, most pedometers need to be attached to a firm waistband; however, some pedometers can be carried in a shirt pocket, pants pocket, or bag held close to the body. Others can be worn on the ankle or in a shoe (Tudor-Locke et al., 2011). Studies report that pedometer-based walking increases physical activity (Williams et al. 2008; Ben, Ugwu, Eneka & Alor, 2019). In a synthesis of studies addressing the use of pedometers to increase physical activity, Bravata and colleagues (2007) reported that on average, pedometer users increase their physical activity by 27% over baseline levels. A key predictor of increased physical activity is setting a step goal (e.g., 10,000 steps per day) for participants. Pedometer-based walking programs are associated with significant decreases in body mass index, body weight, and systolic blood pressure (Bravata et al. 2007; Richardson, Newton, Abraham, Sen, Jimbo, & Swartz, 2008).

Accelerometers capture the steady progression of bodily acceleration, providing detailed information about the frequency, duration, intensity, and patterns of movement. Counts from accelerometers are used to estimate energy expenditure. Accelerometers have been used to provide an objective measure of compliance with physical activity recommendations for the United States population (Troiano, Berrigan, Dodd, Masse, Tilert & McDowell, 2008). Accelerometer technology is now finding its way into newer classes of waist-mounted pedometers and smartphones with the piezoelectric mechanism being

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sensitive to the vertical acceleration at the hip with the capability of data storage over a long period of time (Tudor-Locke *et al.*, 2011).

Heart Rate Monitors are also sensor-based devices used to determine whether or not an individual is in his/her target heart rate zone. This is considered to be 50-85% of your maximum heart rate. This is beneficial to know because it is the zone where one's body is operating most efficiently and frequently burning the most fat. Maximum heart rate is calculated using the simple formula: $HR_{max} = 220 - \text{one's biological age}$. Devices that simultaneously monitor heart rate and body motion provide valid and reliable measures of physical activity of children, adolescents, and adults in free-living conditions (Barreira, Kang, Caputo, Farley, & Renfrow, 2009; Ben *et al.*, 2019). An athlete's preparation for a sport or activity can also be aided by heart rate monitoring technology. This equipment comprises a recorder and a receiver to collect data, and assist a participant in exercising at the required exertion level for best results and safety. The data collected includes the heart rate of the participant when training, time, distance covered, and average and maximum speed. Additionally, it can make comparisons between this data and that of other performances and participants. The data can be graphed visually for an athlete to analyze and monitor their performances, which assists with preparation by allowing an athlete to train with the required intensity, and evaluate what improvements they have made by comparing their results to previous outputs (Heyward & Gibson, 2014).

Interactive Video Games

With exergames emerging and providing individuals with motivational and movement opportunities that produce fitness and health benefits, other video games may assist in knowledge and motor acquisition (Papastergiou, 2009). Videogames such as Dance Dance Revolution (DDR), has revolutionized exergames as means to enhance physical activity levels. According to Coshott, Thin and Young (2009), exergaming is the positive exercise experience gained by combining exercise and multimedia gaming (software and hardware). Positive gains ranging from elevation in the heart rate levels and increment in energy expenditure have been shown in a variety of studies using Dance Dance Revolution (DDR), a well-known dance simulation game by Konami Corporation, where the player is required to dance to a variety of songs, guided by watching scrolling directional arrows on the screen, which correspond to arrows on the pad that he/she has to step upon in synchronization with the music (Sell, Lillie, & Taylor, 2008; Iortimah & Tyoakaa, 2020). Due to dancing being a good aerobic activity, DDR has been used to promote physical activity and weight loss in obese children and adults (Epstein, Beecher, Graf & Roemmich, 2007; Zhu, 2008). As predicted by Zhu (2008), more than 1500 schools in the United States use DDR in physical education classes. Many fitness centres are now offering interactive games to promote physical activity of children, adolescents, and older adults. These interactive games are well suited for playing alone or with others, and they require little training or skill, provide an alternative to exercising in bad weather, and may serve as a transition to actually participating in sports and physical activities however, gaining system should not be considered equivalent to traditional exercises but should be seen as a supplement and not a replacement of traditional exercises. (Chamberlin & Gallagher, 2008; Ben *et al.*, 2019).

A reduction in weight gain, waist circumference, and blood pressure was also reported by some researchers who carried out studies on overweight children who participate in exergaming (Murphy, Carson, Neal, Baylis, Donley & Yeater, 2009; Maddison, Foley, Mhurchu, Jiang, Jull, Prapavessis, Hohepa, & Rodgers, 2011). While a great majority of the exergaming focus has been on children, it also holds promise for promoting functional independence, improving balance, preventing falls, reducing premature disability, and maintaining health by increasing the physical activity levels of adults (deJong, 2010).

Bioelectrical Impedance Device

This is a device for estimating the total body water or fat-free mass using measures of the body's resistance to current flowing through the body. This method requires minimal skill and experience on the tester's part. The machine passes a harmless electronic current through the client's body and records the impedance (opposition) to the current. The current will flow through tissues with a high-water content faster than through tissue with less water, such as fat. An individual who has more fat will record a slower speed for the current. The speed at which the current moves is measured and used to determine body composition. Research has shown that this method has a good level of accuracy with only ± 4 per cent error (Heyward & Gibson 2014).

Digital Video Camera and Visual Analysis Software

The use of the motion analysis system will surely enhance many areas of fitness both in research and instruction. Using a digital video camera has indeed simplified the collection of data as the visual analysis software allows coaches and

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fitness trainers to view captured movements and to analyse them (Anmol, 2014). Software is set of instructions which tells the computer what to do once instructed. There are various kinds of software and applications available in the market with its usage in sports and physical education further classified according to their performed task. Most of the biomechanical analysis software are integrated with number of video cameras (Hemantajit, 2019). Using cameras and computers, an individual or athlete is recorded when performing a movement or skill and his/her motions are analyzed to identify areas for growth. Coaches can identify shortcomings or improper techniques and prepare a program to correct them.

Conclusion

Fitness centres serve as one of sport mediums to improve health and physical fitness. The development of fitness centres in developing countries has generated a lot of positive responses. The positive response is proven by the increasing number of people who love physical activity. Commercial fitness centres present the opportunity to be physically active. The majority of fitness centres offer both group and individual activities (Riseth, Torunn, Tom, & Aslak, 2019). Fitness equipment is a worldwide ever-growing phenomenon and its usage is nowadays popular both in human routines and academic investigations. With access to fitness amenities, instructors, personal trainers, coaches and club operators are well positioned to help bring about a healthier world (Silvio, Jerónimo, Leonor & Jorge, 2020).

Recommendations

1. Individuals should be informed and made aware of the need for active participation in physical activities for optimum health.
2. Development of fitness centres should be encouraged to bring about mass involvement in physical activity irrespective of age groups.
3. Occupational physical activity programmes should be encouraged in order to discourage sedentariness across all sectors.
4. Fitness test measurements should be taken regularly, in order to monitor one's health status.

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